

MoonShots: Mission-Oriented Open Schooling

1. Excellence

„To transition to the 21st century, schools need to take a risk – they need a moonshot”

– Esther Wojcicki, Moonshots in Education (2014)

Open Schooling is a fundamental shift to give students more autonomy and agency in their local community and entrust them with greater ownership of their learning outcomes. Today’s students have the desire and capacity to lead “moonshots” – ambitious, exploratory and ground-breaking projects based on specific and relevant challenges. The fields of space science and its technologies are excellent launch points for “moonshots” in science education that emphasize open schooling. Last July, millions of people worldwide celebrated the 50th anniversary of the very first „moonshot”, the Apollo 11 landing on the Moon in 1969¹. Space, space exploration and travel, and space images have great appeal to large sections of the public (Russo & Christensen 2010). The possibility of life in the universe is deeply embedded in the social imagination of young people (Graham, 2002). Finally, space science and technologies encompass a broad range of formal education subjects including biology, geology, chemistry, physics, engineering, philosophy, and history and demand key skills like creativity, collaboration across sectors, and project management (Pompea & Russo 2019). Space science and technologies impact the daily lives of European citizens in transport, agriculture, weather forecasting, environmental management, and fighting wildfires to name only but a few examples².

The Horizon 2020 call: *Open Schooling and Collaboration on Science Education* highlights the shortfall in science-knowledgeable people at all levels of society. As the European Commission’s Report for Responsible Citizenship (Hazelkorn et al., 2015) points out, the future of European (science) education can be undermined by:

- Wide disparities in participation in science education, in formal, non-formal, and informal settings; Declining interest in science studies and related careers that are essential to meet the demand for well-prepared graduates in the associated fields;
- Insufficient understanding of the wide competencies for using STEAM³ in education;
- Family involvement needed to inspire the curiosity of children;
- Lack of emphasis on creativity and innovation;
- Inadequate public understanding of how science can help meet societal challenges;
- Lack of involvement of community stakeholders.

The *MoonShots* project is designed to address these challenges. This project will motivate and attract the interest of students, family members, young scientists, teachers, and society towards science and science-related careers. Through the Open Schooling Mission-oriented projects, *MoonShots* will transform schools into research and innovation hubs; an energetic community nucleus designed to encourage science and technology careers. With *MoonShots*, schools will become incubators and developers of innovative ideas and collaborations. Student entrepreneurship skills will be promoted using cutting-edge technology infrastructures such as robotic telescopes and satellite data in project development. While our society needs scientific solutions to global, regional, and local challenges, an understanding of the role of science in society remains mysterious to the public. In this project, students will learn to effectively communicate scientific information. This will not only increase informed-decision making by the public, it will also be a key motivator for students to pursue scientific careers.

1.1. Objectives

The main objectives of the proposed project are the following:

01. Establish *MoonShots* based on a Mission-Oriented Open Schooling approach

MoonShots will implement a Mission-Oriented Open Schooling approach following the European Union’s ‘Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union’ strategy (Mazzucato, M. (2018) blended with the Open Schooling methodology originally introduced in the H2020 *Open Schools for Open Societies (OSOS)* project⁴. OSOS has already introduced and tested the OSOS Open Schooling methodology in more than 1000 schools in 10 European countries. To achieve this, *MoonShots* will develop a Mission-Oriented Open Schooling (see section 1.3.2) approach targeted at schools in partnership with community stakeholders, comprising 3 Phases: Phase 1. Open School Challenges Development: Development by the *MoonShots* Consortium of the scope and context of the Grand Challenges and respective Missions; Phase 2. Challenges Journey: could you send me the link with content of openRRHub, and follow-up mentoring on project development; Phase 3. Local Implementation: Local implementation of the selected proposals. The selected proposals will be implemented in schools throughout Europe and beyond, with at least 10 schools per partner country.

02. Support schools in adopting open schooling approaches to tackle societal challenges, based on STEM and community engagement best practices, through collaborations among formal, non-formal, and informal

¹ P2-ULEI coordinated the global celebration MoonLanding50: with reported and over 1 million people directly participating in activities in 128 countries worldwide. Find more information at: www.moonlanding50.org

² https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/space_en

³ STEAM fields are science, technology, engineering, art and mathematics. STEAM is also an approach to integrate STEM subjects into various relevant education disciplines. These programs aim to teach students innovation, to think critically and use engineering or technology in imaginative designs or creative approaches to real-world problems while building on students’ research and innovation skills

⁴ <https://portal.opendiscovery.space.eu/en/osos>

education providers, enterprises, research institutes, policy-makers and civil society

Our approach targets teams of schools with community stakeholders (families, researchers, industry entrepreneurs and professionals, and policy-makers). In the first year, *MoonShots* will launch the Open Schooling Missions; the school-stakeholder proponent teams will submit their concept notes, aimed at tackling these local community relevant missions through multi-stakeholder collaboration. *MoonShots* has identified 3 preliminary challenges: Climate Change, Expanding Horizons: Living in the Solar System, Life in the Universe and corresponding Missions (Table 1.2.). The submitted proposals by the school-stakeholder teams will be reviewed by Mission Boards (see Section 1.3.2), and the selected ones will be supported by an Iteration and Mentorship Programme, which includes a Hackathon, based on STEM and community engagement-best practices, for further development and testing of the proposals.

03. Enhance cooperation across communities worldwide, by involving schools and community stakeholders as active agents in tackling local-to-global relevant societal missions

MoonShots will establish Mission Boards, who will make an initial short selection of proposals implemented locally by the respective teams. The selected projects will be implemented in several school contexts in different countries, and the corresponding tools and resources will be published online in the *MoonShots* Toolkit and available for educators around the world. With this model, schools and community stakeholders from different countries across the world will be able to collaborate effectively.

04. Set-up a network of MoonShots in Europe and beyond, promoting a large-scale awareness-raising mechanism that enhances entrepreneurship, networking expertise, collaboration, and the application of science and technology research to the projects

MoonShots takes advantage of the unique network of our consortium schools: the IAU Einstein Schools (International Astronomical Union, Leiden University) that brings modern science to the hands of students; the Galileo Schools (NUCLIO) that are developing community-wide activities to give educators confidence in using innovative learning models; and the MoonShot, a recently established network of schools (supported by the IAU) which are aiming to introduce an open schooling culture in their settings. The project team will ensure a fair coverage of urban and rural areas in each country. Moreover, the consortium has a great capacity to promote astronomy and space-related activities in educational settings using its extensive networks (e.g.: H2020 OSOS, FP7 Universe Awareness, H2020 Space Awareness, H2020 spaceEU, IAU100 and other large-scale initiatives).

05. Implement advocacy actions towards policy-makers and textbook publishers to develop a legacy and sustainability plan that goes beyond the duration of the project

MoonShots will develop and implement an advocacy and sustainability strategy for Open Schooling, by engaging with national and European policymakers. We will also advocate for resources in school textbooks on this approach in 8 European countries.

To achieve these five important objectives, the consortium brings together expertise from different fields:

- Tens years of global coordination experience for coordinator P1-IAU, leading large-scale science education projects, such as the UNESCO/IAU International Year of Astronomy 2009 and the the P1-IAU Centenary: IAU100, with a large number of educational activities, like the *MoonLanding50* or *Einstein Schools*;
- Expertise in leading large-scale Open Schooling projects: P3-EA is the coordinator of H2020 Open Schools for Open Societies and P2-ULEI is the coordinator of H2020 Open Science Hub Network;
- Over 10 000 schools in Europe and 500 outside Europe. A large networks of formal education experts;
- Non-formal and Informal Science Education Providers and Leaders (Cité de l'espace, Austrian Space Forum, NOA, Trinity College and Science Gallery Dublin, the IAU via its Office of Astronomy for Education, and NUCLIO);
- Enterprises and professional associations in the aerospace field (e.g.: Austrian Space Forum);
- Space and Astronomy Research Centers (University of Antwerp, Leiden University, Trinity College Dublin, National Observatory of Athens);
- Space Business Incubators (Austrian Space Forum, NUCLIO);
- Educational Training Centres (NUCLIO, Leiden University, Ellinogermaniki Agogi, UC Leuven Limburg).

1.2. Relation to the work programme

MoonShots relates to the “Open schooling and collaboration on science education” topic of the H2020 Science with and for Society work programme. It fosters the creation of new partnerships in local communities of science education providers, enterprises and local community stakeholders. It uses astronomy and space sciences, and engaging topics such as GPS and Earth Observations that are relevant to our daily lives. Given their wide appeal both to pupils and to general audiences (as shown by studies of student interests such as “Relevance of Science Education” (ROSE) (Sjøberg & Schreiner, 2010), astronomy and space sciences are in a unique position to “open up” engagement with STEAM subjects in general. These partnerships foster expertise, networking, sharing and applying science and technology research findings across different enterprises, in particular in the field of space and its applications at a national and international level within formal, non-formal, and informal settings. The key challenges that *MoonShots* addresses are those identified by the Call: the increasing shortfall of scientifically literate citizens; the decline in the number of young people pursuing scientific careers; and the decreasing numbers of people who have an understanding of how scientific and technological advancement contribute to our societies. We will foster an appreciation of how the thoughtful uses of science and technology can offer solutions to a large number of problems including health care, environmental protection, transportation, and many more (Rosenberg et al. 2014). *MoonShots* focuses mainly on astronomy and the space sciences not only because they answer fundamental questions about our Earth and its systems, the solar system and beyond, but that they are key drivers of innovation and technological advances in robotics, miniaturization, optics and photonics, high-speed computing, and system modelling. An example activity of a *MoonShots* project is the Dark Skies Rangers Global Initiative (Walker, 2015), an awareness program aimed at students of all ages to stimulate them to make an audit of light pollution and

energy usage in their school/district. Students evaluate the level of light pollution, estimate how much energy is being wasted, and produce a report to be delivered to the local authorities. They are also advised to promote a light pollution awareness campaign to the local community not only about the value of dark skies, but also the effects of excess light on our health and well-being, and those of plants and animals. In *MoonShots*, we extend our understanding using satellite views from space of each involved community. By working jointly with researchers we engage students in innovative scientific experiments using both ground and space-based data.

Another relevant example of the importance of including cutting-edge science in schools and the value of the Open Schooling movement to shape innovation for science education are the IAU Einstein Schools (Pompea & Russo 2019b). The programme promoted hands-on experiences related to modern-day science to students across the world. The experiments enabled students to explore gravity and learn about black holes, gravitational lenses and gravitational waves. Through *MoonShots*, students will go one step further and engage in hands-on research – by using cutting edge research infrastructures such as robotic telescopes – and participate in authentic discoveries – notably of Solar-system bodies such as asteroids – while contributing with scientists in the field. Students will be able to interact with developers of research facilities, learn about the impact on society related to the technological advancements, and experience and understand the importance of STEM in our lives. The scientist-apprentices will then take their excitement to their community and disseminate their discoveries promoting a ripple awareness effect related to science and its importance for our future. Technology plays a key role in the project with topics like lasers, optics, high-speed computing, and computer modelling and simulation being integral (Fig 1.1). There is also a strong emphasis on communication between schools, with the possibility of schools joining together to submit ideas and implement projects.

Figure 1.1. Astronomy is a comprehensive discipline encompassing a broad range of formal education subjects including biology, geology, chemistry, physics, engineering, philosophy, and history and also skills such as collaborations and management. This makes space a natural umbrella science to a more holistic education. Adapted from Pompea & Russo (2019a), based on Miley (2012).

1.3. Concept and methodology; quality of the measures

The main concept behind the *MoonShots* project is to transform schools into research and innovation hubs. As a school seeks innovative ways to improve community outdoor lighting and save energy, it will be communicating those results in town forums, web sites, and meetings. This process of explaining the process of assessing light pollution, the science behind it, the measurements that the school makes in collaboration with industry, and the recommendations from its students for action is an opportunity for science to be in action and applied to a local or regional problem. Similarly, remote sensing data can give students an understanding of climate issues, its implications such as the increased number of wildfires, and a way to communicate what they have learned and possible actions for consideration. Schools will be a reference point for their local communities, contributing towards a more scientifically literate and informed society. This contributes to citizens’ ability to make informed decisions and choices, while also raising students’ appreciation of science, increasing their science literacy and giving them a taste of a science career. *MoonShots* also aims to transform schools into incubators of innovative ideas and into collaboration platforms between relevant stakeholders to promote entrepreneurship skills to students. The existing network of partners’ school-networks (e.g.: OSOS, UNAW, spaceEU, GTTP, Inspiring Science, Belgium Stemmnetwerk) of over 10 000 schools in Europe, will ensure an abundant exchange of ideas, powerful collaborative projects, as well as a rich geographical and cultural distribution.

The project team will set up *Space Incubators and Innovators* hubs in specific sites and will make available to them the necessary tools, support the establishment of the relevant partnerships, and implement the methodology that will allow productive collaboration with local, national and international stakeholders (e.g.: research centres and universities, space business incubators, industry). Families and members of the community at large will also be invited to actively participate in the various investigations proposed by the space explorers in each school. These actions will be accompanied by awareness and dissemination campaigns. In the project’s development and execution the UN Sustainable Development Goals will also be observed, in particular those related to quality education and gender equality, life on land and the environment (see Section 2. Impact). The consortium team has extensive experience and expertise in designing and implementing astronomy and space activities that follow innovative student-centred learning methodologies and cutting-edge technologies in formal, non-formal and informal contexts. Our team includes a mix of research institutions (Leiden University, University of Antwerpen, National Observatory of Greece, Trinity College Dublin), science communication institutes (Cit de l’espace, Austrian Space Forum, National Observatory of Greece), Educational Training Centres (NUCLIO, Leiden University, Ellinogermaniki Agogi, UC Leuven Limburg) and organizations with large networks of schools (NUCLIO, Ellinogermaniki Agogi, UC Leuven Limburg) that are already implementing innovative activities in schools at large scale. The methodology and approach followed by the project is based on practices that project partners have extensive experience with, and which have already proven their impact and added value worldwide. The project runs in parallel with the efforts of the

International Astronomical Union to foster the application of suitable evaluation methods for activities and resources in astronomy education. Through the inclusion of the IAU, and its newly established Office of Astronomy for Education, we will ensure compliance of project evaluation with the emerging community consensus, and in turn aim to give valuable input to the community process.

Indicatively, we mention some of the projects and initiatives our consortium members are/have been part of, and on which will be the starting point for building the MoonShots methodology and related materials:

Table 1.1. Relevant projects and initiatives of which OAstroSchools partners are/have been part of

Project	Description	Relevance for <i>MoonShots</i>
<p>H2020 Open Schools for Open Societies (OSOS) https://www.open-schools.eu/</p>	<p>OSOS provides innovative ways to explore the world: not simply to automate processes but to inspire, to engage and to connect. It supports the development of innovative and creative projects and other educational activities. It transforms schools to innovative ecosystems that act as shared sites of science learning in which leaders, teachers, students and the local community cooperate. (Partners involved: P3-EA (project coordinator), P8-NUCLIO)</p>	<p><i>MoonShots</i> will use the OSOS Open Schooling methodology as a starting point to develop the Mission-oriented Open schooling approach. Additionally, it will use the network of OSOS schools (familiar with the Open Schooling concept) to engage them in the creation and implementation of Mission-based projects.</p>
<p>H2020 Open Science Hub Network (OSHUB.net)</p>	<p>A network of Open Schooling Hubs that contributes to the development, innovation and well-being of underserved communities, by creating community hubs for open collaboration, based on multi-stakeholder collaboration, local relevant challenges are addressed, and have access to resources and tools to develop Inquiry-Based STEAM Education, citizen-science and maker-centred projects. (Partner involved: P2-ULEI [Project coordinator] and P4-TCD).</p>	<p>OSHUB will bring in a network of Open Schooling Hubs to ensure the active involvement of schools in rural areas, areas close to geographical and social borders and underprivileged areas.</p>
<p>Open Astronomy Schools Teacher Training Programme https://open-astronomy-schools.org</p>	<p>Open Astronomy Schools TTP intends to invite teachers and trainers and involve them in a series of challenges and opportunities especially designed for the education community. The project uses the community building approach foreseen in the OSOS (Open Schools for Open Societies) project to involve major stakeholders. (Partners involved: NUCLIO, IAU and Leiden University).</p>	<p><i>MoonShots</i> will use training modules of the Programme and adapt them for teachers that will engage in mission-projects.</p>
<p>IAU Einstein Schools https://www.einstein-schools.org/</p>	<p>This Programme helps schools and students across the world to explore the fascinating force of gravity.. Students can learn about current research on black holes, gravitational lenses, and gravitational waves as they explore the importance of gravity and its effect on stars, galaxies, and light. (Partner Involved: Leiden University and IAU).</p>	<p><i>MoonShots</i> will use the materials and mentorship approach from the IAU Einstein Schools in the project.</p>
<p>Universe Awareness www.unawe.org</p> <p>Space Awareness and spaceEU www.space-awareness.org http://www.space-eu.org/</p>	<p>Active in 63 countries, the programme uses the beauty and grandeur of the Universe to encourage especially young underprivileged children, to have an interest in science and technology and to foster their sense of global citizenship.. Project funded under FP7. (Partners involved: Leiden University, IAU).</p> <p>Both projects aim to inform children and young adults about current research and issues related to space sciences and the numerous career opportunities offered by space. Formal and non-formal educators also benefit immensely from the projects by taking advantage of the many high-quality resources that are easily adaptable to different disciplines and countries. (Partners involved: Leiden University, EA and NUCLIO).</p>	<p>UNAWAVE will offer content on space related themes and input for organizing events focusing especially on rural underprivileged areas.</p> <p>Space Awareness will offer rich content on space related themes as well as content and know-how for the <i>MoonShots</i> MOOC.</p>
<p>IAU astroEDU www.iau.org/astroEDU</p>	<p>IAU astroEDU is an open-access platform that uses the familiar peer-review workflow of scientific publications, to improve the standards of quality, visibility and accessibility of educational activities. Educators can discover, review, change, and share astronomy – and space-related activities for primary and secondary education, and also have their activities peer-reviewed by professionals in education and science. (Partners involved: Leiden University, IAU).</p>	<p>astroEDU will offer a series of astronomy and space-related activities for primary and secondary education that could serve as inspiration for teachers and initial input for the mission projects. Through its platform teachers from <i>MoonShots</i> will also have the opportunity to have their activities peer-reviewed.</p>
<p>Global and European Hands-on Universe (GHOEU) http://euhou.net http://handsonuniverse.org</p>	<p>A programme supported by several Nobel Prize winners, developed by researchers in the field of astrophysics involving a series of exercises where students have the opportunity to explore scientific discoveries. Students involved have the opportunity to explore supernovas, extrasolar planets, discover new asteroids, etc. (Partners involved: NUCLIO).</p>	<p><i>MoonShots</i> will use the exercises that the project has been developing for more than 10 years.</p>
<p>Dark Skies Rangers (DSR) https://www.globeatnight.org/dsr/</p>	<p>DSR aims to combat light pollution by raising awareness among the educational community and local authorities to change lighting systems and preserve the night sky. (Partners involved: NUCLIO, EA).</p>	<p>Demonstrate light pollution via educational activities and offer educational resources on the topic.</p>

<p>Galileo Teacher Training Program (GTTP) http://galileoteachers.org</p>	<p>A network of Galileo Ambassadors and Galileo Teachers established in 100 countries with over 50 000 teachers worldwide. They train teachers in the effective use and transfer of astronomy education tools and resources into classroom science curricula. (Partners involved: NUCLIO, IAU).</p>	<p>Make use of the GTTP ambassador scheme to promote the OAS challenges to teachers worldwide.</p>
<p>BEYOND: Building a Centre of Excellence for Earth Observation-based monitoring of Natural Disasters http://beyond-eocenter.eu/</p>	<p>The BEYOND Center of Excellence develops research and provides disaster management services addressing priorities and needs in South Eastern Europe, Mediterranean, N. Africa, Middle East and the Balkans. (Partners involved: P9-NOA).</p>	<p>Demonstrate how state-of-the-art EO data can help communities that are hit by natural disasters, inform authorities on the optimal locations for renewable energy power plants, or help farmers improve their yields.</p>

The project team builds upon its previous projects and initiatives. It will further develop and refine approaches that have already been tested and proven to work worldwide, and provide a seamless methodology that embraces the ‘Open School’ approach. The approach will be reinforced by embedding it in a concrete training framework with a repertoire of astronomy and space-related outreach activities. Overall, we will ultimately establish a collaborative process between relevant stakeholders in each community, building a more relevant, innovative, and inclusive environment for innovation and decision-making.

1.3.1. Methodology

MoonShots will be mostly implemented using the Bottom-Up approach, which, in line with the experience of the partners in this proposal, is the most effective approach to ensure active participation of educators as agents of change. Nonetheless, a Top-Down approach will also be used to involve policy makers as validators of the overall approach. This involvement will also help ensure the sustainability of the project beyond the lifetime of the funding. *MoonShots* proposes a Mission-oriented Open Schooling (Figure 2) approach following the European Union’s ‘Mission-Oriented Research & Innovation in the European Union’ strategy⁵ blended with the Open Schooling methodology originally introduced in the OSOS project. In *MoonShots*, Missions are the mechanisms for orchestrating meaningful activities for schools, while the OSOS Open Schooling approach is the backbone structure for students to tackle the Missions presented to them (Table 1.2).

Figure 1.2. Overview of *MoonShots* open schooling challenges, with details about the interconnections between the Grand R&I Open Schools Challenges and the Local Open Schooling Mission Projects.

Missions, according to Mazzucato (2018) aim to “provide the means to focus our research, innovation and investments on solving critical problems, while also spurring growth, jobs and resulting in positive spillovers across many sectors”. They lay between grand global challenges (mainly represented through the 17 SDGs) and focused concrete projects. Missions are not expected to be ready-made recipes to achieve objectives and offer solutions, instead they must encourage practitioners to seek multiple solutions using diverse setups and alternative routes towards the objectives set.

Missions stimulate bottom-up research and innovation, involve multiple sectors including end-users and the public, and have a strong societal relevance. Our five key selection and design criteria expect effective Missions to be:

1. Bold, inspirational with wide societal relevance;
2. Imbued with a clear direction: targeted, measurable and time-bound;
3. Ambitious but realistic research & innovation actions;
4. Cross-disciplinary, cross-sectoral and cross-actor innovation;
5. Allowing for multiple, bottom-up solutions;
6. Feasible to implement in diverse local contexts by schools and their communities.

The rationale behind Missions makes it an ideal strategy for introducing and mainstreaming Open Schooling to primary and secondary schools: the focus on research and innovation; the involvement of multiple actors and sectors including the public; its cross-disciplinary nature; and the direct connection to society and global challenges. Aside from working with various stakeholders and local actors, schools can coordinate their projects and have teams of students from the same school unit or other schools productively collaborate.

Phase I: Open School Challenges Development

For *MoonShots*, each Grand Research & Innovation Open Schooling Challenge and respective Open Schooling Missions detailed information will be available so the schools can submit relevant ideas. Detailed information and ancillary material will be developed in the Phase I of the project: Open school Challenges Development. For each challenge and mission,

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe-next-research-and-innovation-framework-programme/mission-oriented-policy-horizon-europe_en

MoonShots will develop: the scope and context for the challenge and respective mission, potential examples and additional resources. Detailed information about participation and evaluation criteria will be available. Following this Mission-oriented strategy, the *MoonShots* project will select a number of space-related grand challenges (Table 1.2) and establish a number of missions under each of them. Schools will uptake these missions and design their own locally relevant projects following the OSOS Open Schooling Approach. *MoonShots* has identified 3 preliminary Grand R&I Open Schooling Challenges (Climate Change; Expanding Horizons: Living in the Solar System; Life in the Universe) as well as corresponding Open Schooling Missions and potential examples of Local Open Schooling Mission Projects at the local school level (Table 1.2).

Table 1.2. Overview of the Open Astro Schools open schooling challenges and respective examples of missions.

Grand R&I Open Schooling Challenges	Climate Change (also one of the EU's Challenges)	Expanding Horizons: Living in the Solar System	Life in the Universe
Open Schooling Missions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon Free Communities in Europe by 2030 Reduce the wildfires by 50% in Europe by 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Live on Mars by 2050 Exploit Resources in the Solar System by 2030 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Find lifeforms in other celestial bodies of the Solar System by 2050 Find biosignatures in exoplanets by 2030
Examples of Local Open Schooling Mission Projects (School level)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local energy consumption/ light pollution (Dark Sky Rangers). Schools discover the exciting science and technology behind Earth Observations (EO); learn about satellite optical data basics; identify different plants according to the different parts of the electromagnetic spectrum; exercise on Fire monitoring (EObservers for a Safer Planet by NOAA). Measure, map, visualize and make audible the resonance mechanism of absorption of IR radiation by molecules like CO₂, CH₄ and H₂O. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Living conditions on Mars including (space-suit and building design for mobility and communication). Circular ecosystems for production of food on Mars. (connected with ESAs Melissa www.melissafoundation.org). Prepare for Mars on Earth through analog research and the AMADEE-20 Mars analog Mission. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn how to find exoplanets in space-mission data archives (e.g.: Kepler, TESS, GAIA). Showcase the importance of cross-field synergies (e.g.: Computer Science) to e.g.: optimise exoplanet searches. Demonstrate the habitability potential of planets in our Solar system and distant stars. Showcase the technologies (e.g.: spectroscopy) that lead to scientific conclusions on the chemical composition and habitability of exoplanets. Help children appreciate the diversity of lifeforms and the essential constituents of life as we know it. Link to searches for extraterrestrial life in the Solar System (e.g.: Mars, Europa) and the hunt for Intelligent Life signatures in distant worlds (e.g.: SETI@home). Demonstrate the scientific approach to searches for life outside Earth.

Phase II: Challenges Journey

For Phase II of the project, teams of schools (students and educators) and local stakeholders will be invited to submit their locally relevant ideas on a digital platform to tackle the Grand R&I Open Schooling Challenges and respective Open Schooling Missions (Figure 1.3 and table 1.3).

Challenge Journey

Figure 1.3. Stages of Phase II: Challenges Journey

Table 1.3. Timeline of Challenge Journey stages, and number of projects per stage.

Timeline	M6-7	M8	M9-10	M11	M12	M13-M24
Stage	Mission Ideas Submission Deadline for submission: End of M7	Peer-review	Iteration and Mentorship	Final Review by Expert panel Selection by mid M11	3-day sprint for 3 teams of 3 students (2 European and 1 Non-European)	Phase II: Local Implementation Local implementation in schools and scaling up 9 projects developed
Number of mission projects	Expected number of ideas submitted: 250 per Challenge	Expected number downselected of mission projects: 30 per challenge	Mentorships per challenge: Specific partners will give mentorship to the mission projects		Selected mission projects: 3 per challenge	90 projects will be implemented and around 200 schools will start implementing the 9 selected projects

Stages of the Challenges

- 1. Submission of Mission-Oriented Project Concept:** *MoonShots* invites gender-balanced school teams of 4 or more students, 1 teacher, and at least 1 local partner to produce a project concept.
- 2. Peer review:** New and existing ideas become better through collaboration, transparent feedback, and iteration. Participants are encouraged to build off of others' concepts, collaboratively share insights and combine ideas in order to innovate. At the end of this Phase it is expected to down select the number of projects per challenge to 50 (at least 30% teams from non-European countries).

3. Iteration and Mentorship: During the Iteration and Mentorship Phase, up to 30 shortlisted ideas per challenge will be invited to further develop their proposals around the Grand challenge. All shortlisted teams will be guided in unpacking their innovations, testing aspects of their idea, and finding ways to gain feedback from those who might benefit from their solutions. The Mentorship programme will include several modules relevant for the development of the project, e.g.: “Community Engagement”, “Maker-centered Approaches”, “Citizen Science”, “Gender Equity”. This will be done by a group of mentors (online and whenever possible with face-to-face meetings). Following the same approach as the EU’s Mission-oriented policy⁶, three Mission Boards (one per challenge) will be responsible for the mentorship of the mission projects.

Whenever necessary partners will provide support in 6 local languages: Dutch (P2 and P10); English (P1, P2, P4); French (P5); German (P7); Greek (P2, P9); and Portuguese (P8)

4. Final Review: At the close of the *Challenge Journey*, shortlisted ideas in each challenge will be evaluated against the eligibility criteria set by the Mission Boards. Three projects per challenge will be selected for a final hackathon where the projects will be further developed forscale-up to schools around the world.

5. Hackathon: During the *Hackathon*, the 9 teams (3 per challenge) selected during the Final Review Phase will further develop their projects through a “Design Sprint”. Each team will build a scalable realistic prototype for their projects and test these with different school contexts. This hackathon should include reflection on “lessons learned” that can be of benefit to other educators developing their own projects; a detailed guide on how to implement these 9 projects through open schooling will be available to educators around the world in a *MoonShots* Toolkit. The results will be distributed to all participating schools.

Phase III: Local Implementation

After Phase II, the local implementation will start. The 30 selected ideas per challenge will be implemented locally by the respective teams, while other schools will be invited to implement one (or several) of the 9 projects further developed in the hackathon. Mission Boards will follow the implementation regularly and the digital platform will allow projects to submit status reports and organise knowledge transfer sessions (e.g.: webinars by experts). The project team will deploy the Design-Thinking methodology originally introduced in the OSOS project to “promote real life projects based upon the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles: stimulating student’s engagement, unlocking their full potential, sharing results and providing access to scientific achievements and designing innovative actions for all students”. The Design-Thinking methodology has 4 steps: FEEL (survey local challenges), IMAGINE (explore possible solutions to address local challenges and develop an action plan), CREATE (implement action plan), and SHARE (share process and project results with school community and stakeholders). This methodology ensures that all missions are tailored to the needs and challenges of different local communities. To ensure equity among the various participants, we use the universal design for learning approach. *MoonShots* incorporates in its methodology (especially through mentorships) the value of after-school and museum programs, the expertise of community professionals in science, engineering, mathematics, computer science, and technology, and the experience and expertise of local government and policy professionals. The concept of open schooling in this proposal also relies heavily on creating learning experiences that apply creative problem-solving skills. Students will learn how to frame and address complex problems using science in formulating potential evidence-based solutions of benefit to society. With such a problem-based and student-centred learning approach embedded in the Open Schooling concept, there is also a natural affinity of the project with start-up and other companies that utilize the wide variety of technological skills.

1.3.2. MoonShots Gender Dimension

The Treaty of the European Union aims to eliminate gender inequality and promote equal opportunities for women. In accordance with the Treaty of Amsterdam (1997) and other EU policy reports (EUR 2002/2), as well as the UN Global Goals, establishing equality between men and women is a project priority. *MoonShots* is committed to incorporating the principles of gender mainstreaming throughout the entire project, giving equal consideration to the different life patterns, needs and interests of male and female participants and project members. *MoonShots* will incorporate a gender lens in its methodology, and will consider how groups, procedures and the focus on innovation may limit women’s participation. *MoonShots* will monitor the representation of genders within the project team and will support consortium members and collaborators with caring-responsibilities by ensuring meetings at family-friendly hours, and facilitating family-friendly working arrangements within all partner organisations. All *MoonShots* events and activities will be inclusive and equitable for all genders and orientations and are developed and executed according to gender equity recommendations (e.g.: using Toolkit from H2020 Hypatia, and examples provided by the IASC Gender Handbook). Gender equity guidelines will be provided to all *MoonShots* partners. Gender balance will be considered in all *MoonShots* activities and participation in activities, including the composition of the Advisory Board (AB). Special attention will be paid to the tutoring programme to get inspiring and successful role models in contact with students. A dedicated member of the AB will be assigned to monitor the gender dimension of *MoonShots*.

2. Impact

2.1. Expected impacts

MoonShots will support students, teachers, enterprises and civil society to work together to respond to challenges through Open Schooling Mission-oriented projects developed and implemented at the local, national and international level. *MoonShots* will develop a pedagogical framework that will assist and support the participating schools in incorporating the Open Schooling approach in their culture through meaningful and innovative step-by-step training and mentorship programs. Through the Mission-oriented Open Schooling approach, schools will be innovation and collaboration reference points for their local communities, contributing also towards a more scientifically literate and informed society. This will motivate and excite students, family members, teachers, and society to the value of science and science-related careers. Since students are part of the scientific enterprise—doing science and evaluating science data (rather than reading *about* science), they obtain a sense of success and an attitude of “I can do science”. This growth mentality is highly conducive science identity formation and the growth of science capital.

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe-next-research-and-innovation-framework-programme/mission-oriented-policy-horizon-europe_en

MoonShots and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals

By considering the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in designing our activities, we actively contribute to the targets set in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development⁷. Of the 17 SDGs, we proactively incorporate at least 4 SDGs directly in our activities:

- **SDG4: Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.** *MoonShots* will implement inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities. The project targets educators, young people whose scientific and technical potential are frequently not realised (girls, migrants, and underprivileged youth), parents (disadvantaged families, migrants and ethnic minorities). In this manner, we address targets⁸ 4.1, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, and 4.7 of SDG4 through our activities and outreach to relevant audiences.
- **SDG5: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.** *MoonShots* activities will promote role model women in STEM professions, STEM activities for youth, trainings for educators and will address the question of gender equality in science and technology. Our actions are directly relevant for Targets⁹ 5.1, 5.5 and 5.B of SDG5.
- **SDG13: Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impact.** *MoonShots* will emphasise the importance of tackling climate change through activities directed at primary and secondary school, as well as the Challenge: Climate Action. Both relate to target 13.3¹⁰ of SDG13¹¹.
- **SDG16: Promote peaceful and inclusive societies.** By using the enormity of space to give a unique perspective about our planet to children when their value systems are being formed, we shall build and maintain partnerships across countries and cultures and foster a sense of European and world citizenship.
- **SDG17: Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.** Establishment of the various partnerships within *MoonShots* will contribute directly to targets 17.6¹², 17.16 and 17.17.

2.1.1. Short term impact: 0-2.5 years

MoonShots will promote partnerships and activities between the education community, families, researchers, professionals from industry, and enterprises (namely from the space sector) with the main goal to attract students to STEM subjects and STEM careers and guide them towards studies in STEM fields. In the short term, this will contribute to a society that is more literate, supportive and interested in research and innovation, motivating teachers and students at different ages and education levels to engage with research and innovation through a Mission-Oriented Open Schooling approach. At the same time, *MoonShots* will foster the awareness and interest of students from a variety of backgrounds in exploring science careers, and potentially increasing the numbers of scientists and researchers in Europe, as outlined by the Call.

School students (General)

Target audience: Students in primary and secondary school (6-18 years old). *MoonShots* will dedicate specific approaches and activities targeted at girls and underprivileged youth (see below).

Actions: *MoonShots* will achieve maximum impact among school students through a series of direct activities that appeal and are relevant to young people. Through the development and implementation of mission-oriented projects, students will be engaged in meaningful STEAM experiences, based on Grand Challenges and Missions defined by the European Commission, that will have a direct impact in their communities.

Impact estimators: At the end of the project (M36), 100 000 students have been reached by *MoonShots*, on average 5 000 students through the Open Schooling Mission-oriented Project Development process, and 95 000 via the *MoonShots* Toolkit both in schools, as well as in non-formal settings. At least 90% of all students reached by *MoonShots* activities will be aware of STEM and space-related careers. *MoonShots* will collect data about the participation of students in *MoonShots* activities according to the guidelines provided by Work Package 5: Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation.

Female students

Target audience: Female students in primary and secondary school (6-18 years old).

Actions: We address the current and future shortage of skilled workers in high-tech fields by teaching STEAM subjects with an interdisciplinary cohesive approach emphasizing critical thinking skills needed in the high-tech workforce. This will be achieved through the composition of the teams and by highlighting female researchers, entrepreneurs and professionals from industry and enterprises in *MoonShots* projects and resources. This exposure allows children to imagine these specific occupations as an option for everyone, removing barriers that discourage children in choosing for STEM. *MoonShots* will ensure that children and teens understand that gender distinctions do not need to constrain their interests and dreams. Whenever possible, *MoonShots* will establish links with other projects promoting gender balance in the space sector (e.g.: Space Girls Space Women project¹³). A dedicated module on “Gender equity” will be included in the mentoring program.

Impact estimators: By carefully designing activities that are gender-neutral and provide a positive attitude towards the role of females in space professions, *MoonShots* expects to reach around 50 000 female students (50% of the number of students expected to be reached out).

Underprivileged youth

Target audience: Youth from underprivileged communities (i.e.: ethnic minorities, migrants and disadvantaged youth).

Actions: *MoonShots* aims to advance the educational achievements and STEAM-career aspirations of youth from underprivileged communities through meaningful engagement in STEAM and a strong foundation in STEAM-based literacy and skills.

7 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld>

8 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg4#targets>

9 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg5#targets>

10 Target 13.3 Improve education, awareness-raising and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning.

11 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg13>

12 <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdg17#targets>

13 <http://www.spacewomen.org/about/>

During the divulgation phase of the Open Call for proposal submission, the *MoonShots* consortium will make sure to reach out to schools that serve underprivileged communities. Also, during the implementation and scaling-up phase of the 9 final projects, these schools will be invited to test these projects in their own schools and communities.

Educators (Teachers and informal educators)

Target audience: educators (teachers of primary and secondary schools and other relevant education stakeholders)

Actions: The manifold approach of targeting educators coupled with their influence on career choices are important tools for enhancing the impact of the project. *MoonShots* will engage educators directly through the Mission-oriented Open Schooling call, which includes proposal development, mentoring program, local implementation of the projects, the hackathon and *MoonShots* Toolkit. Also, *MoonShots* will produce a MOOC targeted at educators (formal and non-formal) and school managers, aimed at providing the tools to implement Open Schooling and Mission-oriented projects with students. *MoonShots* tools and resources engage educators in using STEAM to tackle mission-based challenges, with local-to-global impact, through multi-stakeholder collaboration between students, researchers, local enterprises and industry, families, civil society and policy-makers. All *MoonShots* resources will be localized, released as open access, and made available on relevant repositories, such as Scientix. These resources will also include training on gender equity. *MoonShots* will liaise with European educational textbook publishers to encourage them to use Open Schooling approaches and Mission-oriented resources in their educational material across school subjects. This action will enhance the reach of educational resources and have a large multiplying effect. *MoonShots* will also reach out to other education stakeholders, such as after-school programs, museums and science centers.

Impact estimators: At the end of the project (M36), 8 500 educators have been reached by *MoonShots*, on average 1 000 educators through the Mission-oriented Open-Schooling call and mentorship programme+hackathon, 5 000 via the *MoonShots* Toolkit and 2 500 through the MOOC, both in schools, as well as in non-formal settings. *MoonShots* will collect data about the participation of educators in *MoonShots* activities and other relevant information according to the guidelines provided by Work Package 5: Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation.

Community stakeholders: researchers/entrepreneurs/industry professionals/civil society members

Actions: *MoonShots* will promote the establishment of partnerships between schools and university researchers, enterprises, industry, local businesses and civil society, in the context of the Mission-oriented Open Schooling projects. By developing projects with global reach and with strong local impact in their communities, students will gain experience with problem-solving for real-life situations and projects, while contributing to raise scientific literacy and awareness. In order to achieve a wide range of local impact, with added European value, *MoonShots* will strive to select a diversity of projects with different societal goals, for example: research projects, through the development of community-based participatory projects or citizen science projects; entrepreneurship projects that involve local businesses and meaningful responsible actors from the private sector; and social innovation projects, in collaboration with civil society organizations engaged in social inclusion and environmental sustainability.

Impact estimators: *MoonShots* will involve around 250 Researchers/entrepreneurs/industry professionals/civil society members from different sectors. 30 partnerships will be established between schools and universities, enterprises, industry, local businesses and civil society. At least 500 local community actors will also be engaged throughout the project. *MoonShots* will have a diverse representation and at least 50% of female researchers/entrepreneurs/professionals participating in the projects. *MoonShots* will collect data about the participation of universities, enterprises, industry, local businesses and civil society in *MoonShots* activities and other relevant information according to the guidelines provided by Work Package 5: Learning Assessment & Impact Evaluation.

Families and General public

Target audience: Families including those of diverse and disadvantaged backgrounds and cultures (i.e. ethnic minorities, migrants) and European and global societies.

Actions: *MoonShots* will spread awareness to a broad segment of society, by incentivizing and enforcing the involvement and engagement of citizens, namely of families, during the implementation of the mission-oriented projects. Community engagement will not only be a criterion for project selection, but it will also be fostered during the mentoring phase with a module dedicated to “Community Engagement?”. Moreover, the open schooling projects will be simultaneously oriented by the challenge-oriented mission and focused on local relevant issues, and as such will ultimately contribute to local development and well-being. The *MoonShots* Toolkit that will be produced for the 9 final selected projects (3 per challenge) will be disseminated worldwide, so that any community in the world has the tools to implement it locally. This will also promote the sharing of knowledge and experience between communities and citizens.

Impact estimators: At the end of the project (M36), 50 000 citizens have been reached by *MoonShots*.

Policy makers

Target audience: Policy makers on local, regional, national and EU level

Action: *MoonShots* will bring additional benefits for local and/or regional government, as it will promote local development and innovation by connecting schools with research and innovation clusters to tackle local relevant challenges through the mission-oriented open schooling projects. An important activity that we shall employ to increase the impact of *MoonShots* and ensure long-term sustainability is intensive lobbying activities within National and EU institutions demonstrating the societal relevance of a Mission-oriented Open Schooling approach, both at the local and global levels, by bridging communities across the world in tackling global issues with local relevance. *MoonShots* will produce a set of policy briefings on key aspects for *MoonShots*, namely on Open Schooling and community development. Policy briefs are the preferred form of communication of policy actors. These activities will be based on the consortium experience of working with policy-makers (e.g.: Members of the European Parliament) during the H2020 EU Space Awareness, and FP7 EU-UNAWA projects.

Impact estimators: *MoonShots* will reach around 200 policy-makers at the local, national and European level.

Media

Target audience: Traditional Media (Journalists) and Social Media (Digital Opinion Leaders)

Action: Whenever possible local and national media will be invited to *MoonShots* events and activities, like the local implementation of projects, in collaborations with the local communities. National media will also be invited for the hackathon with the 9

final selected projects. A number of press releases will be issued by all the partners (coordinated by WP6 – Communication & Dissemination). *MoonShots* will make policy-briefings available on the website, which can serve as background information for journalists. *MoonShots* will also target media specialized in children and young people, through the World Summit On Media For Children Foundation, and *MoonShots* will promote Space Scoop content to media outlets targeting children.

Impact estimators: Taking into account the media engagement from similar projects we expect to reach around 10 000 people through traditional media. Based on the experience from social media engagement through similar projects in which the consortium has been involved (e.g.: H2020 OSOS or spaceEU) we expect to reach around 250 000 people through social media.

2.1.2. Medium to long-term impact: 2.5-10 years

A mission-oriented strategy provides a massive opportunity to increase the impact of research and innovation, to grasp the public imagination, to foster collaboration amongst multiple actors across different disciplines, and to make real progress on complex challenges that have a real impact on citizen's life. This makes it an ideal strategy for introducing and mainstreaming Open Schooling to schools of primary and secondary education, as it provides a mechanism for embedding higher order objectives and global challenges, which are also locally relevant, through meaningful pathways that promote connections with stakeholders in their communities. This approach is a vehicle for supporting students and teachers as active agents in their communities and getting across the message that such local-to-global challenges can only be addressed and met through the seamless collaboration between experts from different science disciplines, engineering, technology, innovation and societal sectors. By combining this Mission-oriented approach with a pedagogical framework that will assist and support schools incorporating the Open Schooling approach in their culture, and that promotes community engagement toward local development and innovation, *MoonShots* will provide students and citizens with the tools and skills to make informed decisions and choices to improve their communities. Ultimately, by supporting schools as collaboration hubs in their own communities, through research and innovation, and by positioning students as innovators and problem-solvers, students will realize the importance and impact of science on society and on citizen's daily life. As such, the Mission-Oriented Open Schooling approach of *MoonShots* will motivate the interest of students towards science and science-related careers and inspire them to consider taking up science careers. Moreover, the development of an advocacy and sustainability strategy for *MoonShots*, by engaging with national and European policymakers and textbook publishers, will ensure a wider reach of the *MoonShots* strategy both spatially and temporally. It is expected that some students participating in *MoonShots* activities will be selecting their post-secondary school studies and careers related to space within 5 years of the closure of the project. *MoonShots* activities will increase participants' awareness of and interest in science careers. Data will be collected to provide a baseline measurement for such long-term studies and „longitudinal assessments“. It is expected that *MoonShots* activities will have an impact on **students' career decisions**, contributing towards the ERA objectives of increasing the number of scientists and researchers in Europe, **and specifically increase the number of students that opt for education paths in the fields of science, technology, engineering and mathematics, and in the long term, a science career, perhaps related to space or innovation.** The proposed methodology will be used as a reference point for educators, teacher trainers, stakeholders and people working in formal and non-formal education settings (i.e.: science museums) to allow them to introduce the rationale of open schools in their school community through authentic and innovative activities that promote science and celebrate the bond between science and society. Using the *MoonShots* methodology, different parties (schools, science museums, local community organizations, universities, etc.) will have a roadmap that will allow them to make contact with open schools and work with them under a common collaboration framework with distinct roles and a clear understanding of each party's part. Our activities and methodology will promote the idea of open schools where students can act as science ambassadors, contribute to raising the local community's awareness on science related matters and making real contributions towards the improvement of the citizens' well-being through their projects. To ensure the effective participation of multiple parties and the establishment of a robust and strong community of practice, the project team aims to achieve the following indicators:

Indicator	Target Value
Minimum number of countries involved	28 (EU) + 20 (outside EU/EU Associated countries)
Minimum number of schools involved	280 (EU) + 200 (outside Europe)
Minimum number of teachers, educators, teacher trainers involved	~ 8 500
Minimum number of students engaged	~ 100 000
Minimum number of citizens engaged	~ 50 000
Minimum number of researchers/entrepreneurs engaged	~ 250
Minimum number of stakeholders, policy makers engaged	~ 200
Minimum number of local community actors engaged	500

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